

Temperature measurements on overhead lines using Fiber Bragg Grating sensors

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Abstract—This paper shows the results of temperature measurements on an overhead power transmission line segment under controlled conditions using Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors. An optical fiber with three FBG sensors enclosed in copper was characterized in temperature and then attached along an overhead transmission line to perform the measurements. It was found that variations due to wind and environment temperature can be as high as 30°C and that those variations increase as current and conductor temperature increases and sometimes exceeding the maximum allowable.

Keywords—Overhead power transmission lines, Fiber sensors, Fiber Bragg Grating sensors, temperature measurement

I. INTRODUCTION

When rating Overhead power transmission Lines (OHL), temperature and sag are main constraints due to clearance to ground and objects, and the conductor material maximum allowable temperatures. Both are correlated since the rising in the conductor temperature produces the elongation of the conductor thus increasing sag and decreasing clearance[1]. Moreover, if OHL are operated at high temperatures for long periods, it causes premature ageing of its conductors as a result of permanent elongations (Creep) and loss in strength due to annealing of the material [2].

Conductor temperature depends on many factors such as Joule effect, environment temperature, wind speed and direction, humidity, solar radiation and the radiation and absorption coefficients of the conductor that vary along the line and through time [3], [4]. For those reasons, OHL are traditionally rated statically supposing worst case conditions of line load and weather to keep the temperature of the conductor under its maximum. Nevertheless those conditions have low probability of occurrence hence the line is generally underrated and in some cases, the risk of exceeding the maximum temperature of the conductor exists [2], [3], [5].

Given the rising energy demand from users, the introduction and growth of renewable energy sources, local generation and the difficulty to install new OHL, Dynamic Line Rating (DLR) has gained more interest in order to increase OHL efficiency taking advantage of the moments where conditions are favorable [4]. As an example, in Colombia OHL are statically rated and according to a study carried out by [6] at Guavio-Tunal line, "...transmission lines

can carry 70.9% more current using DLR regarding static rating..."

In DLR, temperature of OHL conductors needs to be measured or calculated [7]. Some methods have been proposed and tested to calculate OHL conductor temperature from the measures of sag, tension and weather conditions [1]. Some other methods measure OHL conductor temperature indirectly because of the difficulty of electric sensors to withstand high voltages. Another method uses sensors attached to the line like the power donut that collect energy from it and transmit data using RF. One the problems of these sensors is that they could lack of energy when line is low loaded and transmission delays due to network congestion[8].

Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) based temperature sensing is another way of direct temperature measurement that can be applied on OHL [9]. Since those sensors are optical fiber sensors, they have same advantages as optical fiber: are electrically passive, insensitive to electromagnetic interference, and are low in size and weight. Furthermore, as FBG sensors are built on optical fiber core, several sensors can be made in the same fiber thus only one energy source is necessary for all the sensors in the same fiber. In addition to fiber optic advantages, FBG sensors have linear response to temperature and strain, and their measurement information is wavelength coded so they are immune to power fluctuations and insertion losses [10]. FBG sensors have also been used in OHL to determine the Aeolian vibrations via strain measurements [11].

In this article, an application of FBG based temperature sensing in an OHL under controlled conditions is presented in order to show the possibility of integrating this technology as a part of a management system for Colombian electric power network. In section 2 the operating principle of FBG sensors is explained. Sections 3 and 4 show the experimental setting and results respectively.

II. FBG SENSORS OPERATING PRINCIPLES

FBG sensors consist of periodical changes in refraction index along the optical fiber core, created by radiating a photosensitive single mode optical fiber (generally germanium doped) with UV light. Those changes make the FBG sensor to reflect a particular wavelength (λ_B) that match the Bragg condition [10]:

$$\lambda_B = 2\eta_{eff}\Lambda \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Transmission and reflection spectra of FBG sensors

In (1) η_{eff} is the effective refractive index and Λ is the period of the perturbation. Both are sensitive to strain and temperature so if strain or change in temperature is applied, a wavelength shift will occur on reflected light (Fig. 1).

Wavelength reflected from FBG sensors, is detected using an Optical Sensing Interrogator which mainly consist of a broadband or tunable light source, a circulator or coupler and a peak detection and processing block that can be an interferometer, tunable filters, or another FBG [12] (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Typical structure of an Optical Sensing Interrogator

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENT

An optical fiber with 3 FBG sensors built in was used. Each FBG sensor was inserted inside a 2mm diameter, 15cm length copper tube. This copper tube is used in order to avoid strain effects on the sensor since it is attached to the OHL but the fiber inside is not and can expand freely. The optical fiber was attached to an OHL segment placed inside the campus of the Universidad Nacional de Colombia used for testing, which is 6 meters long and 3 meters high, with the FBG1, FBG2 and FBG3 sensors at meters 2, 3 and 4 and wired with an All-Aluminum Alloy Conductor (AAAC) of 48.69MCM codenamed 'Alton' as shown in Fig. 3.

One of the sensors along with the conductor were covered with a thin vinyl layer of less than half a millimeter, to see the effects of thermal insulation in the sensor.

Fig. 2. Experiment setting

IV. RESULTS

A. FBG sensor characterization

FBG sensors were characterized in temperature in order to obtain the characteristic curves of wavelength vs temperature. The results of the characterizations can be seen in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Characteristic wavelength vs temperature curves of FBG sensors

Fig. 4 shows that all three sensors have linear responses and almost the same slopes. The main difference between them is the wavelength offset at 25°C. TABLE I. contains the parameters of each sensor

TABLE I. FBG SENSOR CHARACTERISTICS

Sensor	$\lambda @ 25^\circ\text{C}$ (nm)	Sensitivity (pm/°C)
FBG 1	1557.7135	10.9
FBG 2	1562.707	10.6
FBG 3	1567.4776	10.9

Due to the encapsulation of the sensor, it is expected that the sensor has a higher thermal inertia, consequently they were also characterized in time. This was done heating the sensor to

a constant temperature and then removing the heating source and allowing the sensor to reach room temperature. The results are depicted on Fig. 5. In this figure is shown that the sensors have the time response of a first order system and for a step change in temperature of 30.9°C (from 56.6°C to 25.7°C), it takes 45 seconds to reach 37.1°C (36.8%) which is the time constant (τ) of the sensor, therefore in 180 seconds (4τ) the sensor will be within the 2% of its final temperature.

Fig. 4. Time response of sensor FBG 1

B. OHL temperature measurements

The experiment was performed in four stages, in the first 20 minutes, the line was not energized, then, a current of 42 amperes was applied until the minute 70 followed by an increase to 73 amperes and in the last 20 minutes the line was de-energized again.

Fig. 5. Temperature of the OHL trough time with step changes in current

Fig. 6 shows the results of the experiment with an average window of 1 minute (60 samples), it can be seen that the line increases its temperature when the current is increased due to the Joule effect, and the variations in temperature were caused mainly by the cooling effect of the wind, since there were no significant variations in solar radiation, and as the figure shows, the effects of wind affected more to the FBG2 and FBG3 sensors which were without the vinyl layer while FB1 sensor, covered with a thin vinyl layer, where less influenced by the wind and allowed the OHL to reach higher temperatures.

Fig. 6 also shows the environment temperature (T_{env}) measured in some instants of the experiment, showing that

environment temperature variations were low compared to OHL temperature variations with a constant current

In some points of the figure during the third stage of 73 Amperes, the conductor temperature exceeded the maximum allowable temperature of 75°C, starting to produce a premature ageing of the conductor. The time and magnitude of this conditions are monitored on installed OHL for maintenance purposes.

The maximum, minimum and temperature variation for each sensor in each stage of the experiment are shown in TABLE II.

TABLE II. MAXIMUM, MINIMUM AND VARIATION TEMPERATURES RECORDED

		First Stage	Second Stage	Third Stage	Fourth Stage
Current (A)		0	42	73	0
Temp. max (°C)	FBG1	27	42	83	77
	FBG2	27	39	76	66
	FBG3	27	39	68	63
Temp. min (°C)	FBG1	22	27	68	20
	FBG2	22	24	46	19
	FBG3	22	24	46	20
Variation Temp. (°C)	FBG1	5	15	15	57
	FBG2	5	15	30	47
	FBG3	5	15	22	43

TABLE II. shows that the thermally insulated section of the line corresponding to the sensor FBG1 has higher temperatures, but concerning to temperature variations, in the first and second stages, the variations in temperature are the same for the three sensors, but in the third stage, where temperatures were higher, the temperature variations increased due to the effect of the wind on the sensors.

For the fourth stage, which was disconnection, all three sensors stabilized at 20°C and can be seen that the line takes about 20 minutes to reach its final temperature.

From TABLE II. can be seen that in stage 3, two of the tree sensors have temperatures above 75°C which is the maximum temperature allowed for the ‘Alton’ conductor rated at 85Amp at 75°C with sun and no wind.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This experiment shows that the system measures the temperature changes in the OHL caused by the current and wind effects with good time resolution and can be used as a part of a temperature monitoring system for dynamic rating purposes.

Temperature variations were seen in the OHL because of wind effect, so is expected that in a longer lasting experiment as an effect of intense solar radiation, rain and nighttime, higher changes in temperature can be seen. For that reason

more experiments of longer duration and in different seasons are going to be performed to measure the influence of variable weather conditions in the variations of the OHL conductor temperature and then the temperature of the conductor will be controlled varying the current in order to see how much current can be transported by the conductor without exceeding its maximum temperature and compare the results using static ratings.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank COLCIENCIAS by the support of this project.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. C. E. Jupe, D. Kadar, G. Murphy, M. G. Bartlett, and K. T. Jackson, "Application of a dynamic thermal rating system to a 132kV distribution network," *IEEE PES Innov. Smart Grid Technol. Conf. Eur.*, pp. 1–8, 2011.
- [2] G. J. Ramon, "Dynamic thermal line rating summary and status of the state-of-the-art technology," *IEEE Trans. Power Deliv.*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 851–858, 1987.
- [3] E. M. Carlini, S. Favuzza, S. E. Giangreco, F. Massaro, and C. Quaciari, "Uprating an overhead line. Italian TSO applications for integration of RES," *4th Int. Conf. Clean Electr. Power Renew. Energy Resour. Impact, ICCEP 2013*, pp. 470–475, 2013.
- [4] Q. Li, M. Musavi, and D. Chamberlain, "Overhead conductor thermal rating using neural networks," *SMFG 2011 - IEEE Int. Conf. Smart Meas. Grids, Proc.*, pp. 139–142, 2011.
- [5] A. K. Kazerooni, J. Mutale, M. Perry, S. Venkatesan, and D. Morrice, "Dynamic thermal rating application to facilitate wind energy integration," *2011 IEEE PES Trondheim PowerTech Power Technol. a Sustain. Soc. POWERTECH 2011*, 2011.
- [6] J. Rosero and J. Chinchilla-Guarin, "Impact of Including Dynamic Line Rating Model on Colombian Power System," pp. 36–40, 2016.
- [7] D. Balango, B. Nemeth, and G. Gocsei, "Predicting conductor sag of power lines in a new model of dynamic line rating," *33rd Electr. Insul. Conf. EIC 2015*, no. June, pp. 41–44, 2015.
- [8] D. J. Spoor and J. P. Roberts, "Development and Experimental Validation of a Weather-Based Dynamic Line Rating System," *Ieee*, 2011.
- [9] R. Chintakindi and S. P. S. Rajesh, "Vital role of FBG sensors - 2012 developments in electrical power systems," *Proc. 2013 Int. Conf. Power, Energy Control. ICPEC 2013*, pp. 478–483, 2013.
- [10] A. Othonos, "Fiber Bragg gratings," *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, vol. 68, no. 12, p. 4309, 1997.
- [11] L. Bjerkan, "Application of fiber-optic bragg grating sensors in monitoring environmental loads of overhead power transmission lines.," *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 554–560, 2000.
- [12] J. Chen, B. Liu, and H. Zhang, "Review of fiber Bragg grating sensor technology," *Front. Optoelectron. China*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 204–212, Jun. 2011.